

Bringing the Memories Home: Indigenous Data Sovereignty in the Preservation of Residential School Photos

Sadie Anderson
Indigenous Archivist
sadie.anderson@usask.ca

Jessica Ye
Metadata Librarian
jessica.ye@usask.ca

Historical Context

In 2015, the Truth and Reconciliation Commission of Canada (TRC) released their final report which concluded that the establishment and operation of residential schools was a central element in Canada's cultural genocide against Indigenous Peoples. The residential school system was funded by the government and operated by religious institutions to assimilate Indigenous children into Euro-Canadian culture. These children were taken from their families and subject to abuse, disease, malnourishment, experimentation, and forced assimilation into colonial behaviors. The number of deaths is in the thousands and many of these children were buried in unmarked graves which are still in the process of being discovered. The survivors gained life-long trauma from these experiences which turned into intergenerational trauma that rippled through their communities and led to The Indian Residential Schools Settlement Agreement, the largest class-action settlement in Canadian history, and the creation of the TRC. This context is important for understanding the gravity of the situation and the significance of the University of Saskatchewan (USask) being in possession of residential school photo albums.

Project Background

The University Archives and Special Collections (UASC) has four restricted photo albums dating between 1906 and 1963 that pertain to the students and staff at the Lebret Indian Residential School. The school affected the Starblanket First Nation, Peepeekisis Cree Nation, Okanese First Nation, Little Black Bear First Nation, and Métis people in and around Lebret, Saskatchewan, Canada. The albums were donated to Special Collections by a non-Indigenous USask faculty member, but the provenance and custodial history of the albums is unclear. They were digitized for preservation and became restricted from public access pending community consultation after they were moved to the University Archives in 2021.

After her hiring in 2024, Sadie Anderson found her grandfather in four different photos within these albums, all of which neither she nor her mother had seen before. This prompted the idea for a community engagement to ensure communities are aware of the existence of these photos, correct and enhance metadata records, and seek guidance for stewardship decisions around the photos all while in keeping with traditional Indigenous protocols and practices. Jessica Ye was brought onto the project due to its metadata / digital component. This engagement gave the rest of Sadie's community a chance to have similar experiences, to see loved ones who are no longer with them or whom they never got the chance to meet. By sharing these photos with Indigenous communities whose children attended this school, we centered the resilience and agency of the survivors. Instead of being subject to colonialist narratives, these communities have the power to tell their own stories and re-contextualize these photos.

Acknowledgments

Community Engagement Team

Tim Hutchinson, Lindsay Stokalko, Alycia Bockus-Vanin, Cassius Goulet, Myles Shingoose, Dallas Pelly, Jenelle McArthur

kēhtē-ayak and Cultural Helpers

Cliff Davis, Gail Starr, Edith Starr, Patricia Dieter, Beverley Poitras, Lawrence Pinay

Participants' Nations

Starblanket First Nation, Peepeekisis Cree Nation, Okanese First Nation, Standing Buffalo First Nation

Findings

- Participants want us to return and share with more community members.** Because the event occurred at the same time as the Treaty 4 Gathering, this meant more people were in the Lebret area. However, it also meant potential participants were away at the Gathering and could not attend this event.
- Survivors want their stories to be remembered and are willing to share information once trust has been established.** Because we began in the event *in a good way*, in a way that honours Indigenous protocols and demonstrates our sincerity and commitment to reciprocity, this helped establish trust between us and community members. This made knowledge sharing / data gathering a respectful and more productive process.
- Stewardship requires both physical and digital considerations for access and preservation.** When asked about future stewardship, participants made suggestions such as: a digital monument / online access portal, a physical monument at the site of the school, repatriation / repatriation through First Nations' governance bodies, restricted viewing in the University Archive, relocating the items to a closer local archive, etc. Physical and digital preservation are inextricably linked. Options need further exploration with community.
- Indigenous data sovereignty and community consultation should be central to the digital preservation process when the data is about or created by Indigenous Peoples.** OAIIS asserts that the aim of preservation is to ensure that digital objects remain accessible and usable by the designated community. In this case, the designated community has particular cultural needs and a specific historical context that needs to be taken into account when it comes to access, use, and how the objects are understood.

Objectives

- To share photos from the Lebret Indian Industrial Residential School with the community
- To name unnamed people, correct incorrect names and information, and share and collect memories of loved ones
- To decide what happens to the physical photos and digitized files, including where they should be housed and if/how they should be repatriated/repatriated
- To decide how future updates on this project will be communicated and how the data collected will be shared

Guiding Principles

- Community Based Research Practices
- Indigenous Research Methodologies
- OCAP® (Ownership, Control, Access, Possession)
- CARE Principles
- Traditional First Nation Knowledge protocols
- United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP)
- Steering Committee on Canada's Archives Reconciliation Framework

Event Structure

- As participants entered, they were given consent forms and honoraria.
- An Indigenous Social Worker and cultural helpers were present as mental health supports.
- Pipe ceremony and prayer was held to start the event. Breakfast and lunch was served under blessed food protocols.
- Copies of the photographs were printed and sorted into binders by category. Binders with photos of clergy and staff were clearly labelled kept at Table 3. All other binders circulated freely at the tables. Original photo albums were available for viewing at a separate table.
- Sticky notes and pencils were provided for taking down names alongside *Transcription Approval Forms* for recording memories. Research team members sat with participants to help record data.